

Some Recent Advances in Separation Processes in Polymeric Media[†]

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Some recent advances in separation techniques involving polymeric systems have been discussed. The areas that have emerged predominantly over the past ten years. Such as polymeric mechanochemical devices, of separations, polymeric adsorbents, stress induced polymer separations, separations of protein or polymer solutions through size selective water absorbing polymer gels *etc.*, have been focussed. Some contributions from the National Chemical Laboratory have been cited.

IN the field of separation technology, a number of cases where separations involve polymeric systems in one form or the other have been emerging in a very dominant way. The first case naturally relates to areas where polymers themselves act as separators (for instance, membrane processes). The second one relates to those where separations in polymeric media are conducted. Stripping of polymeric melts containing trace impurities of monomers (as in ethylene/molten polyethylene case) could be cited as a specific example. The purpose of this brief review is to provide a rather broad classification of these processes and then dwell on some of the more exciting findings in recent years. Wherever possible, a reference will be made to the contributions from the polymer science and engineering school at National Chemical Laboratory.

The area where polymers themselves are used as separators comprise polymeric membranes, polymeric ion-exchange resins, polymer flocculants *etc.* As regards the separation processes in polymeric systems, a number of areas can be cited. These include solvent or monomer stripping from molten polymers, concentration of polymeric or protein solutions through the use of new water absorbing polymers, separation of macromolecules by using finite stress fields *etc.* It is impossible to provide an exhaustive coverage of systems falling in both the above categories. Therefore, we will focus rather sharply on the following areas only, where some exciting advances have been made in recent years.

- (i) New developments in polymeric mechanochemical devices, which act as chemical valves for affecting separations.
- (ii) Some recent advances in polymeric adsorbents.
- (iii) Separations of dilute protein or polymer solutions through size selective water absorbing polymeric gels.
- (iv) Stress induced polymer separations.

It is believed that although the field of separation processes in polymeric media has been exhaustively studied, the above areas have emerged predominantly over the past five to ten years, and no comprehensive coverage of these exciting developments is to be found in the literature.

Membrane separations—a quick overview :

Before dealing specifically with mechanochemical membranes, it might be useful to take a quick bird's eye view of the area of membrane separations in general.

By contrast with the widely used methods of distillation, freezing *etc.*, the separation of mixtures by membrane techniques does not involve phase conversions of the components being separated. The operations are normally carried out at ambient temperatures. Consequently, membrane methods are very economical and have low energy requirements. For example, in desalination of water by reverse osmosis, the consumption of thermal energy is significantly less than that for running a distillation system. Similarly, the energy consumption for obtaining oxygen enriched air by membrane methods could be up to 50% less than that in the cryogenic methods. The unit capital investment for the construction of membrane type separating devices is comparatively small and the period of recoupment is short too. In some cases, particularly in microbiological and medical preparations, satisfactory separation of mixtures with a change in the properties of the components may be found to be impossible except by membrane methods. The drawbacks of the membrane type separation methods includes the need for preliminary purification of the system being separated in order to avoid contamination by particles in suspension. Furthermore, there are no all purpose membranes and membranes of different compositions and morphology will be required for separation of different systems.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

It is not intended to provide a complete review of the membrane separation processes and such reviews already exist in the literature¹⁻⁴. For a given separation process, there is a bewildering range of membranes. For instance, numerous kinds of polymers in combination with solvent and other additives are used for preparation of membranes for specific purposes in reverse osmosis. For example, composite membranes have become very popular. Table 1 shows a broad classification of

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE SEPARATION TECHNIQUES

Reverse osmosis	
Dialysis	
Electrodialysis	<i>Dense membrane</i>
Piezodialysis	
Gas permeation	
Pervaporation	
Ultrafiltration	<i>Porous membrane</i>
Microfiltration	
Extraction	<i>Liquid membrane</i>
Enzymatic reaction	
Facilitated transport	<i>Chemically active membrane</i>
Detection of chemicals	

membrane separation processes and Table 2 shows some examples of polymers used for preparation of reverse osmosis membranes. Membrane technology has made extensive inroads into various fields. Table 3 shows some of the industrial applications of membrane processes. In a given process, there may be number of alternatives and these could depend very much upon the operating conditions, raw materials and desired separation products.

The use of a membrane technology involves the solution of a whole complex range of scientific, technological and design problems. These include the study of mechanism of kinetics and transport of liquids and gases in membranes and the development of the corresponding quantitative theories, the development of and modification of new types of polymeric materials, development of new techni-

TABLE 2—MATERIALS FOR MEMBRANE

Reverse Osmosis

Asymmetric Membrane

- Cellulose acetate
- Aromatic polyamide
- Polybenzimidazole
- Aromatic polyhydrazide
- Polyamidiimide
- Sulphonated polyphenylene oxide
- Polyhydantoin
- Polymidazopyrrolone

Composite Membrane

- (Polyethylenimine+TDI)/polysulphone (NS-100)
- Furfuryl alcohol/polysulphone
- (Polyethylenimine+isophthaloyl chloride)/polysulphone
- (Epichlorohydrin+ethylenediamine+isophthaloyl chloride)/polysulphone
- Furan resin/polysulphone
- Sulphonated polyfurfuryl alcohol

ques and equipment for production of commercially usable membrane systems, etc. It could also involve the development and organisation of production of auxiliary materials for separating elements and equipment and also of special pumps, compressors, filters etc. for preliminary purification of systems, monitoring and measuring devices and automation facility, the designing of final membrane modules etc. It is thus evident that a mere synthesis of polymeric membrane material in the laboratory is not just adequate and a total integrated effort has to be launched.

Mechanochemical polymeric devices :

Some exciting developments have been reported in the past few years, which relate to permselective membranes in which the mechanochemical contractile forces exhibited within the membranes enlarge the pore size isothermally and lead to a marked increase in water permeability and improved performance of macromolecular separations.

TABLE 3—SEPARATION TECHNOLOGY AND INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

	Reverse osmosis	Dialysis	Electrodialysis	Ultrafiltration	Microfiltration	Gas permeation
Desalination	++	—	++	—	—	—
Ultrapurification of water	++	—	—	+	++	—
Treatment of waste water	++	—	+	++	++	—
Recovery of reusable materials	++	++	++	++	—	++
Salt production	—	—	++	—	—	—
Purification of foods industries	++	++	++	++	++	—
Purification in pharmaceutical industries	—	+	+	+	++	—
Production of chemicals	—	—	++	—	—	++
Medical equipment	+	++	—	++	++	++

+ ≡ Less preferred, ++ ≡ More preferred.

The novel mechanochemical system converts chemical into mechanical energy by polymer-polymer complexation between complementary polymers^{5,6}. Such dilations and contractions in these systems are related to the drastic conformational shrinkages of a three-dimensional network consisting of polymethacrylic acid (PMAA) due to a reversible complexation with solved polyethylene glycol (PEG). Osada and Takeuchi⁷ have demonstrated that in the presence of a small amount of PEG, PMAA membrane loaded with 100 times the weight of the dry membrane could contract and dilate many times to over 90% of its length. The work done per contraction by one gram of contractile substance was 5×10^{-3} cal, and the membrane exhibited more than 2000 g cm^{-2} of stress when the contraction was performed under constants membrane dimensions, *i.e.* under conditions of isometric contraction.

A natural corollary of the above observation is that if the mechanochemical contraction is developed isothermally, the contractile stress appearing in the membrane should expand the pore through which the water and macromolecular solute permeates. Thus conceptually it is possible to obtain ultrafiltration membranes having mechanochemically expanding and contracting pores. Fig. 1 shows the effect of a mechanochemical contraction of the PMAA membrane on water permeability when a small amount of PEG with a molecular weight of 3 000 was subsequently added to water. It was seen that the PMAA membrane exhibited a

Fig. 1. Effect of mechanochemical contraction of the PMAA membrane on water permeability when PEG is added to water

marked increase in water permeation as soon as the membrane was contacted with the PEG solution. Once the PMAA membrane is treated with PEG, the water permeates the membrane with a high velocity. On the other hand when the membrane is rinsed with alkali (pH 8) to dissociate the complex and remove PEG, the membrane recovers the initial low water permeability.

The increased water permeation in the presence of PEG is due to the expansion of pores because the water permeability bears the same relation to the molecular weight of PEG as the work done by the contractile membrane or the stress generated under isometric contraction. This is demonstrated in Fig. 2, which shows the dependence of water permeability (1), relative contraction (2), and stress (3) of PMAA membrane on the molecular weight of PEG. K_0 and K denote the permeability constant for PMAA membrane treated and untreated with PEG, respectively. The presence of a maxima, when PEG reaches a molecular weight of 3 000 in

Fig. 2. Performance of a mechanochemical membrane as a function of the molecular weight of PEG

every curve in Fig. 2, indicates that the membrane-PEG complexation takes place not only on the surface, but inside the wall membrane as a result of the penetration of PEG molecules through the expanded pore channel. Osada and Takeuchi⁷ observed that water soluble polymers other than PEG capable of forming complexes with PMAA, such as polyvinyl pyrrolidone, polymethyl vinyl ether, polyvinyl alcohol *etc.* could neither contract the membrane nor increase the water permeation.

Thus, the mechanochemical PMAA membrane can behave as a 'chemical valve'.

As regards the tests of such mechanochemical devices with haemoglobin and albumin solutions, some data are presented in Fig. 3. It is seen that both protein solutions can permeate the membrane without decreasing the high permeation velocity for pure water released by the PEG, whereas in the case of a PMAA membrane treated with PEG the protein clogged the membrane rapidly thereby reducing the permeability. Osada and Takeuchi⁷ observed that the mechanochemical membrane could improve the performance of protein separation by about 240 times for albumin and 55 times for haemoglobin in comparison with PMAA membrane which was not treated with PEG.

Fig. 3. Performance of mechanochemical membranes for haemoglobin and albumin separations.

Ultrafiltration processes, have not found extensive application because of the unavailability of membranes, which combine permeability with high permselectivity. The inherently high water permeability of the mechanochemical membranes plus its controllable permselectivity to water soluble solutes can potentially lead to practical ultrafiltration membranes. The successful development of such 'chemical valves' may therefore open up a new area of separation.

Polymer adsorbents :

Synthetic polymers are being increasingly used to remove organic species from an aqueous medium by physicochemical adsorption and also for extraction of metals. They apparently offer some major advantages in both these processes. Indeed novel polymers which coordinate to metals are likely to offer the possibility of providing the basis for the next major phase of development of extraction and

separation processes. In some cases, they may even offer an advantage over conventional solvent extraction and ion-exchange processes for separating metals. For instance, solvent extraction, in which a metal is extracted into an organic phase, is particularly used for the concentration above 200 ppm whereas ion-exchange is useful below 100 ppm. Polymers with metal coordinating ability could be useful over the entire concentration range that is from trace concentration upwards. Moreover, the polymers can be designed to be extremely selective to precious or base metals in many conditions of concentration, pH or temperature. The utilisation of these polymers has led to the developments which have a commercial potential. Their use as scavengers of precious metals certainly appears to be promising.

When focussing on separation of organic molecules by polymeric adsorbents, it has to be emphasised that the binding energies of synthetic polymers are lower than those of activated carbon for the same organic molecules. These lower binding energies help in providing easy recovery of polymeric adsorbents by regeneration^{8,9}. Whenever the economics of solvent or chemical regeneration of adsorbent is favourable, the use of polymeric adsorbent could be advocated. An additional advantage of polymeric resins is that they have durable matrices as compared to conventional adsorbents, such as activated carbon.

Polymeric adsorbents find a special use in the adsorption of many organic pollutants from the waste water. A comprehensive summary has been provided¹⁰. The choice of these adsorbents will depend upon the factors such as the nature of the organic components, presence of electrolytes in waste water, pH of the solution *etc.* Systematic studies on polymeric adsorption have appeared in the literature^{11,12}. Such adsorbents can be regenerated by changing the pH or by using a solvent. The reagent used should be such that the sorbate can be easily recovered or the sorbate regenerant mixtures can be recycled to the main process. To regenerate an adsorbent resin loaded with the solute, a solvent system should be chosen such that the solvating forces of the solvent for the solute will overcome the adsorbent resin attractive forces. The solute can then migrate to the solvent phase. We shall now discuss some of the specific applications of polymeric adsorbents.

For adsorption of phenol from various waste waters, cross linked polymethylacrylate resin, crosslinked polystyrene and vinyl pyridine-divinyl benzene copolymer can be used for adsorption of phenol from various waste waters⁹. Kowabata and Ohira¹³ found that if porous copolymers of vinylpyridine and divinylbenzene with large areas can be used then the adsorbent capacity of the resin can be further increased. *p*-Nitrophenol, chlorinated phenols and other phenolics can also be separated by using polymeric adsorbents⁹.

In the area of recovery of metals by using polymeric adsorbents, a number of advances are continuing. An interesting one was reported by Husband and Rowley¹⁴ recently. They observed that fulvic acid, which is one of the humic components of soil is an important natural chelator of metals and as such implicated in the mobilisation of metals in soils and in natural waters. They further observed that maleic anhydride can be polymerised in the presence of either tertiary phosphines or tertiary amines and the polymer produced by initiation with pyridine was very similar both spectroscopically and in many of its other properties to fulvic acid. By binding poly (maleic anhydride) to polystyrene, they undertook experiments on lead recovery. Laboratory scale experiments showed that it had an excellent capacity for Pb^{II} and could adsorb it upto 0.42 mmol g^{-1} of adsorbent, while adsorbing Mg^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in trace quantities. The adsorbent could be easily regenerated for reuse by treatment with $2 M$ nitric acid. Given the potential of the material as a lead scavenger and current concern about lead toxicity, the polymer may prove useful in practical water treatment applications.

Some polymeric resins have also been used for uranium recovery from sea water. The oceans contain 4.5×10^9 tons of uranium and it is conceived that about 10^8 tons in the upper 100 m of the ocean is immediately accessible for recovery. Number of studies on large scale feasibility of uranium recovery from sea water by synthetic polymer adsorption, especially of the acrylonitrile-divinyl benzene-copolymeric amidoxime resin have been attempted. They appear to show good promise. The concentration of uranium in the sea water is quite low (3 g dm^{-3}) and therefore, the economics of such processes has not been found to be viable so far. However, new innovations in adsorbent synthesis could change the picture dramatically.

Polymeric gels as size-selective separators :

The problem of separation processes focussing around concentration of dilute solutions of organic or biological materials is becoming increasingly important. Specific examples include the removal of water from starch and cheese whey, the concentration of antibiotics in fermentation broths and the recovery of protein products of genetically engineered microorganisms. Various methods have been used for concentrating dilute solutions of macromolecules. Electrophoretic and ultrafiltration techniques *etc.* have been commonly used on laboratory scale. Interestingly, a new concept of using cross-linked gels to concentrate solutions of high molecular weight solutes has emerged recently. Such gels are size-selective and they can concentrate solutes whose size exceeds a certain minimum. The resulting separation process provides an interesting alternative to ultrafiltration. In ultrafiltration, a polymer membrane separates a solution at high pressure from a solvent at low pressure.

Solvent is forced through the membrane from high to low pressure, while the solute is retained and thus concentrated. This one step process is conceptually simpler than the polymeric gel process to be described later. However, it has the disadvantage that the concentration polarisation near the membrane implies large pressure drops and expensive equipment. Additionally, the possibility of the macromolecules, such as proteins and DNA being subjected to harmful shearing stresses¹⁵ is quite real.

Two concrete efforts on concentrating dilute solutions of macromolecular systems will be described here. The first effort at National Chemical Laboratory uses a crosslinked acrylate gel, whereas the one from the Minnesota (U.S.A.) school relates to using a hydrolysed crosslinked polyacrylamide bead, which is produced commercially as a packing for gel permeation chromatography. These studies, which almost appeared at the same time in the open literature, indicate the powerful potential of the techniques.

Vartak *et al.*¹⁶ synthesised crosslinked acrylate gels which had a capacity to pick up water to the extent of 150 g g^{-1} . The polymerisation was carried out in glass tubes and after polymerisation the gel sticks were used as such for concentration of macromolecules. Proteins having a wide range of molecular weights ($10\,000$ - $450\,000$) were concentrated using the gel sticks. About ten-fold concentration of different proteins was attained and the recoveries were also rather high (Table 4). They found that the gel sticks could be effectively used for concentrating other high molecular weight substances also such as starch, carboxymethyl cellulose, DNA *etc.* Vartak *et al.* found that low molecular weight compounds, such as glucose, sucrose, acetic acid, methanol and other inorganic solutes did not concentrate. It was postulated that this property of the gel could be made use of to eliminate product inhibition in some of the enzyme catalysed reactions which are inhibited by low molecular weight products. Vartak *et al.* also focussed their attention on the process of cellulose hydrolysis and looked at the problems of recovery and reuse of cellulase from the hydrolysis reactor, since the economics of solution hydrolysis could presumably be improved by improving the separation techniques. As is well known, the separation of enzymes from the soluble products, such as glucose from the cellulose hydrolysates presents a problem. They performed experiments on concentration of cellulase and the recovery of glucose from a mixture of cellulase and glucose. They found that the enzymes could be concentrated to 30-fold with about 90% recovery. The recovery of glucose was about 75%. Such a method, if found technologically successful, could provide an important direction to the recovery of cellulase and glucose from the cellulose hydrolysates.

Cussler *et al.*¹⁷ went a step further in providing a technologically viable scheme for using cross-

TABLE 4—CONCENTRATION OF MACROMOLECULES USING DRY GEL STICKS*

Macromolecule	M _r	pI	Experimental pH	Concentration mg ml ⁻¹		Recovery %
				Initial	Final	
Subtilisin inhibitor	10 000	5.9	7.5	800 ^a	6 200 ^a	85
Cytochrome c	12 500	10.8	12.3	0.1	0.8	80
Myoglobin	17 000	7.2	9.8	0.5	3.7	81
Soybean trypsin inhibitor	21 000	4.5	7.5	0.25	2.0	80
Bovine serum albumin	68 000	4.9	7.3	0.5	4.1	90
Ferritin	450 000	4.6	7.5	0.05	0.05	90.4
CM cellulose	—	—	6.0	10.0	82.0	90
Starch	—	—	6.0	5.0	41.0	84
DNA	—	—	7.5	0.02	0.16	80

* Ref. 16. ^a Concentrations of subtilisin inhibitor expressed in units/ml.

TABLE 5—CONCENTRATION OF DILUTE AQUEOUS SOLUTION USING HYDROLYSED POLYACRYLAMIDE GELS*

Mol. wt. solute	Dalton	Solute size nm	Feed conc.	Raffinate conc.	Efficiency**
Polystyrene latex	—	990	0.21	0.35	85
Bovine serum albumin	66 000	7.2	0.082	0.183	93
Haemoglobin	64 500	6.2	0.73	1.26	91
Polyethylene glycol	3 000-3 700	3.8	0.56	1.09	91
Sucrose	342	0.84	1.00	1.09	6
Urea	60	0.53	3.00	3.00	0

* Ref. 17. ** Defined as (measured increase in concentration) × (raffinate volume) / (initial solution volume).

linked gels as size-selective extraction solvents. Observing that swelling characteristic of the gels is a strong function of the pH of the surrounding solution, they designed an elegant regeneration step. Small gel spheres are added to a dilute solution containing macromolecules. As the spheres swell they adsorb the low molecular weight solvent but exclude high molecular weight solutes. The raffinate, now concentrated in the high molecular weight solutes, can then be separated from the swelling gels by filtration. Using gels whose swelling is a very strong function of pH, addition of an acid would collapse the gel volume and release much of adsorbed solvent. The collapsed gel is then separated from the released solvent by filtration and added to a small amount of base, gel can then be added to a fresh solution where it will swell again. Some of the results on concentration of dilute solutions using such polymeric gels obtained by Cussler *et al.* are shown in Table 5. It is readily seen that excellent efficiency of separation is achieved especially for higher molecular weight solutes. In particular, it was seen that solutions which are greater than 3 nm in diameter could be concentrated with an efficiency of at least 80%. These efficiencies are reduced by weak solute adsorption on the surface of the gel spheres. For example, for the 34.6 nm polystyrene latex, some latex adhered weakly to the gel surface. When this latex was removed by washing, the reported extraction efficiency was 97%. In this sense, the gel extractions are similar to freeze concentration techniques used in the food industry, where solutes can adhere to ice crystals. For such techniques

to be technologically viable, repeated use of the gels should be possible. Cussler *et al.* have provided data which show that for upto 12 cycles of regeneration there was practically no change in the latex concentration efficiencies. They noticed that there was a little cumulative loss due to the latex adsorption on the gel. This adsorption, which is responsible for inefficiencies, is apparently most significant for the first cycle and is less important as the gel is reused. There is an obvious limitation on the cut-off point with respect to the solute-size. However, the work at National Chemical Laboratory indicates that by increasing the density of crosslinks in the polymeric gels it should be possible to shift this point. If the gel interacts equally with water and with the protein solute, it will still absorb only the water, because the protein is too large to diffuse between the gels crosslinks. As a result, gels would be like extraction solvents whose selectivity will depend on differences in rates of diffusion. The development of these gels could open up a new era of separation technology. Considerable research for lowering the cut-off point for separation appears to be necessary.

The disadvantage of solute loss due to adsorption essentially occurs due to the direct contact between the water absorbing gel and the solute. Besides, the batch mode of operation has an inherent disadvantage. Recently, Kulkarni *et al.*¹⁸ have developed an improved separation process, which eliminates these drawbacks. Fluxes of the order of 0.8-1.4 kg/m² h atm have been reached, such devices show a considerable promise for future developments.

Stress induced separations :

There is a growing awareness now that macromolecules tend to migrate whenever there is a variation of shear rate in a following medium. More precisely stated, in any non-homogeneous deformation field it is impossible to maintain a uniform polymer concentration for a sufficiently long length of time. A number of possible mechanistic explanations for such changes have been reported in the literature and we shall summarise some of these. What is important to appreciate is the possible role that such phenomena might play in practical separation systems.

Some suggestions attributing the phenomena of polymer migration to the changes in entropy arising out of the deformation of the molecule had appeared in the sixties^{19,20}. The essence of the proposed hypothesis was that in a deforming liquid, the macromolecules would stretch and thus create free energy differences in different positions within the fluid. More specially, in a non-uniform flow field, the entropy and free energy would become position dependent. In order to compensate for such free energy changes, concentration gradients would be induced. The end result is that polymer molecules would migrate towards regions of low stress level. If a polymer solution was to flow through a capillary then a polymer depleted low viscosity layer will be formed adjacent to the wall through which the high viscosity liquid might appear to slip through.

Recently, several researchers²¹⁻²⁴ have laid major stress on developing a quantitative description of such hypothesis. Metzner²⁵ developed the following expression for the concentration difference adjoining a stagnant region (2) and flowing region (1) of a dilute polymer solution,

$$\ln \frac{C_2}{C_1} = \frac{\tau \underline{\tau}}{2RT C_1}$$

where, C is the concentration, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature and $\underline{\tau}$ is the deviatoric stress. Since $\tau \underline{\tau}$ is always positive, the above equation suggests that with an increasing intensity of stress field, the concentration in the stagnant region is increasingly higher when compared to that in the flowing liquid. The above development has a very important consequence in a number of areas and some of these are summarised below.

Secondary oil recovery :

The most important field in which the phenomenon of polymer migration may have a major influence is the flow through a porous medium. Oil recovery, for example, employs water soluble polymers as mobility control agents for the flowing liquid used to drive out the oil trapped within the porous reservoir structure. Among various other complexities associated with polymer flow through porous media, polymer retention is a critical factor

affecting the oil recovery. Although retention can be due to noncontinuum effects, like adsorption and pore blockage, separation due to polymer migration from the flowing stream to the relatively stagnant dead end pores is quite possible. In fact, the observation by petroleum technologists in the case of flow of a polysaccharide and polyacrylamide solutions through different porous media shows evidence of such polymer separation and retention²⁷.

Size exclusion chromatography :

Size exclusion chromatography involves flow of polymer solutions through packed columns wherein the fluid is subjected to an ill-defined non-uniform flow field. The resulting macromolecular migration and consequent separation therefore significantly alters the elution characteristics. The flow rate dependent elution characteristics reported exhaustively by Aubert and Tirrell^{28,29} confirm this behaviour.

Polymer fractionation :

If the argument about entropy induced changes leading to polymer molecule separations is correct then such a mechanism should tend to a fractionation of polymer molecule with respect to molecular weight along the radius of a capillary. The possibility of molecular fractionation was experimentally studied by Shreiber and Storey³⁰ using polyethylene melt extruded through a capillary and a microtonic procedure to obtain peripheral layer of the polymer. They observed as high as 40% reduction in molecular weight of this outer layer as compared to that of the whole extrudate. Whitlock and Porter³⁰ undertook similar measurement of capillary extrusion of polystyrene and again obtained differences in molecular weight. However, the influence of stress induced polymer fractionation was somewhat negligible. It is quite possible that the flow lengths used by Whitlock and Porter were insufficient. The degradation effects might also complicate the situation further.

An exciting shear field flow fractionation technique (shear FFF) has been described recently by Giddings and Brantley³¹. The configuration of the device is a concentric cylinder system with the inner cylinder rotating. The axial motion is superposed on the rotational motion. Simplified analysis indicates that a molecular fractionation with very high selectivity can be attained rather easily. In fact maximum selectivity factors of 3 could be achieved, which are better than all other separation techniques, such as sedimentation FFF(1), thermal and flow FFF(0.5), steric FFF(0.30) and size exclusion chromatography (0.05 to 0.22).

Concluding remarks :

In the foregoing, we have summarised some of the recent advances in separation techniques that have emerged over the past few years. A number of these prove the 'scientific feasibility' of the concepts, but we are sure that with continued

research efforts, these could prove to be 'technologically viable' and open up a new era of separation processes.

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